

Impact of Problem-Solving Strategy on Performance in Concept Respiratory System using Stem Model among Secondary School Students in Zaria Educational Zone.

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Abstract

This study investigated the Impact of Problem-Solving Strategy on Performance in Respiratory System concept using STEM model among Secondary School Students in Zaria Educational Zone. A quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pretest, posttest control group was adopted for the study. The population consists of 1821 (Male, 900 and Female, 921) Senior Secondary School Two (SSII) Biology students during the 2021/2022 academic session in Zaria Educational Zone. A sample size of 100 (Male, 50 and Female, 50) Senior Secondary two (SS2) Biology students was obtained for the study. This was arrived at using Random sampling technique to select two sample schools from the target population. Hence, an intact class was used in each of the two sample schools. The test instrument used to measure performance was Biology Performance Test (BPT). The BPT consist of 40 multiple choice test items in Respiratory System concept with four options A-D. The findings showed that significant difference exists in performance of the students taught using problem- solving strategy with STEM model and lecture teaching method and students taught respiratory system using problem-solving strategy with STEM model performed better than those taught using lecture teaching method. In conclusion, it was found that problem-solving strategy with STEM model improved performance of students better than the lecture teaching method. It was recommended that Biology teachers should be encouraged to explore problem-solving strategy using STEM model to improve academic performance of students.

Keywords: Problem-solving strategy, STEM model, Lecture teaching method, Respiratory system, Academic Performance

Introduction

In today's conditions, the factor that enables the economic development and progress of countries is innovation in technology. For this reason, it is of great importance to train the next generation as science and technology literate and to make engineering common (Miaoulis, 2009). Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) education is defined as a pedagogy that involves multidisciplinary field of learning, as it provides learners with purposeful and comprehensive real-life learning experience. Moreover, the main objectives are based on students' abilities to perform and apply the learnt skills in an integrated way as well as to bridge the gap between learners, knowledge providers and industrial demands (Kunalan, Cheah, Moses, Er & Ng, 2018).

STEM is an educational approach based on the idea of educating students in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics with an interdisciplinary approach. STEM provides interdisciplinary interaction by emphasizing activity-based learning. STEM aims to raise individuals who have high self-confidence and strong communication skills, can think creatively, solve problems, know how to use tools, understand mechanisms and come up with original ideas (Nağaç & Kalaycı, 2021). Some of the subjects that are targeted in scientific literacy under STEM include chemistry, biology and physics with the technological literacy portion focusing on the development. For STEM to be successful, special teaching strategies and approaches are necessary. The teaching and learning process of the STEM approach entailed inquiry-based and problem-based learning methods, which could increase the students' understanding and thinking skills with regard to problem-solving questions. Thus, the use of the STEM approach in the teaching and learning process encourages students to interact and fosters the value of collaboration between students and their ability to think critically. Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) education has a potential to give a great impact to the worldwide education system, especially in engineering education (Kunalan, Cheah, Moses, Er & Ng, 2018).

Teaching strategies are an important factor in producing good quality education and concerns the academics as well as the higher education institutions. Traditional teaching style is outdated especially when it comes to engineering education. Therefore, pedagogy in the classroom needs to be reformed in 21st century education. A study on instructional techniques in STEM education especially on digital information or E-learning reviewed that it will trigger an active role of students in the classroom (Kunalan, Cheah, Moses, Er & Ng, 2018). Conventional methods are the more frequently used teaching methods in

comparison with the STEM approach. Comparisons were made between treatment groups, which include students who participated in the adapted learning methods, and the control groups, which include students who participated in the conventional methods (Kong & Mohd, 2022). Evidently, students in the treatment groups were more motivated and confident to pursue learning than those in the control groups using conventional methods (Huang, Su, Yang & Liou, 2017; Kumar, Chang & Chang, 2018; Mohd, Tarmizi, Abu, Luan, 2014). The use of conventional methods was also found to yield low student engagement and achievement (Fatah, Suryadi, Sabandar & Turmudi, 2016; Minarni, Napitupulu & Husein, 2016). Hence, based on the literature review, conventional methods should integrate with other learning methods to enhance students' motivation and achievement in STEM.

The STEM approach is a student-centred teaching and learning process that involves an inquiry process in problem-solving questions (Kong & Mohammed, 2022). STEM pedagogy explains the teacher's role within STEM instruction. The teacher guides students to examine problems from all angles by questioning. This pedagogy involves the philosophy that students are capable of guiding their own learning. Teachers are just there to facilitate this student-led process. Students use hands-on, practical applications of content in order to solve their challenges (Margot & Kettler, 2019). STEM education includes student use of math and science concepts they have learned in an applied setting through the use of engineering design and technology. Instead of being taught in a vacuum, math and science are brought to life through their need to be used in order to solve a real problem (Chamberlin & Pereira, 2017). In this research, problem solving teaching strategy was used as the STEM teaching strategy.

Problem-solving is how to learn independently, it is the most convenient approach to achieve the aims of teaching learning process (Ali, 2010). Problem-solving is an important activity in the teaching and learning of science related courses. It is a complex activity that engages a variety of cognitive components and skills. Problem-solving is an investigative task whereby the solver explores the solution path to reach a goal from given information (Adeoye, 2010). In the problem-solving learning, the students turn from passive listeners of information receivers to active, free, self-learner and problem solvers. It also shifts the emphasis of educational programs from teaching to learning. It enables the students to learn new knowledge by facing the problems to be solved instead of feeling boredom. Problem-solving is a deliberate and serious act, involves the use of some novel method, higher thinking and systematic planned steps for the acquisition set goals (Yuzhi, 2003; Mangle, 2008).

Problem-solving as a strategy of teaching may be used to accomplish the instructional roles of learning basic facts, concept and procedure, as well as goals for problem-solving. Problem-solving can stimulate the interest and enthusiasm of the students (Ali, 2010). According to Adeoye (2010), when problem-solving strategy and conventional methods were used in teaching physics, problem-solving students had higher achievement scores than conventional method students. There exist positive and meaningful increases in the achievement of students using instruction activities towards developing metacognitive skills. The students with a higher level of metacognitive skills become successful in problem-solving.

The teaching strategies in the current STEM structures are not effective in linking the student to the real-world situations. The instructors have often been described as not being hands-on minded in the training of students as required in the policy that brought STEM into existence. This situation has led to suggestions of change in the STEM classrooms. According to WAEC Chief Examiner's Report (2022), the performance of Biology students in the year 2022 was worse than the previous year. This failure was attributed, to among other reasons, lack of in-depth knowledge of some basic topics and terms that border around respiratory system, genetics, classification, among others. In line with this, the concept of respiratory system has been reported by researchers (Abe & Owoeye, 2016; Mapulanga & Chituta, 2018) to be perceived by students as difficult. As a result, this study was conducted to determine the impact of problem-solving strategy with STEM model on performance in respiratory system concept among secondary schools.

Objective of the Study

Specifically, the study seeks to achieve the following objective.

Determine the mean performance score of students taught respiratory system using problem-solving strategy with STEM model and those exposed to lecture teaching method.

Research Question

This study was guided by the following research question;

What is the mean performance score of students taught respiratory system using problem-solving strategy with STEM model and those exposed to lecture teaching method?

Hypothesis

HO1: There is no significant difference in mean performance score of students taught respiratory system using problem-solving strategy with STEM model and those exposed to lecture teaching method.

Methodology

A quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pretest, posttest control group was adopted for the study. The population consists of 1821 (Male, 900 and Female, 921) Senior Secondary School class two (SSII) Biology students during the 2021/2022 academic session in Zaria education zone. A sample size of 100 (Male, 50 and Female, 50) Senior Secondary two (SS2) Biology students was obtained for the study. This was arrived at using Random sampling technique to select two sample schools from the target population. Hence, an intact class was used in each of the two sample schools. The test instrument used to measure performance was Biology Performance Test (BPT). The BPT consist of 40 multiple choice test items in Respiratory System concept with four options A-D.

Results

Research Question One

What is the mean performance score of students taught respiratory system using problem-solving strategy with STEM model and those exposed to lecture teaching method?

The research question one was answered using mean and standard deviation as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Means and Standard Deviations of Student’s Performance Scores in the problem-solving with STEM model and Lecture teaching method Groups

Groups	N	Mean	SD	MD
Experimental	50	37.20	13.41	5.12
Control	50	32.08	13.43	

The result in Table 1 shows that students taught using problem-solving strategy with STEM model group had higher mean performance score of 37.20 than those in the lecture teaching method group with mean performance score of 32.08 with a mean difference of 5.12.

Hypothesis one

HO1: There is no significant difference in mean performance score of students taught respiratory system using problem-solving strategy with STEM model and those exposed to lecture teaching method.

The hypothesis was analyzed using t-test at $p \leq 0.05$ alpha level. The result is presented in Table 2.

Table 2 t-test Analysis of Students’ Performance in the problem-solving Strategy with STEM model and lecture method Groups

Groups	N	Mean	Df	p-value	Remark
Experimental	50	37.20	98	0.05	Significant
Control	50	32.08			

Significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Table 2 reveals a significant difference between the mean performance score of students taught respiratory system using problem-solving strategy with STEM model and those taught using lecture teaching method. This is because p-value of 0.05 obtained is equal to the alpha level set at $p \leq 0.05$. The significant difference is in favour of students exposed to Problem-solving strategy with STEM model. Therefore, the null hypothesis one which states there is no significant difference in mean performance scores of students taught respiratory system using problem-solving strategy with STEM model and those exposed to lecture teaching method, is hereby rejected.

Discussion

In the test of hypothesis one, the performance of students taught using problem-solving strategy with STEM model and lecture teaching method were compared. It was found that Problem-solving with STEM model group had a mean score of 37.20 and had higher performance score than the lecture teaching method group with a mean score of 32.08 as shown on Table 1.

It was found that using problem-solving strategy with STEM model increased performance of students than the lecture teaching method. This might be due to interaction of students with each other when solving problems, handling of concrete instructional materials which made the students obtain some skills like discovery and scientific thinking. Similarly, the students did not only have opportunity to discuss and share their views, they had the privilege to compare and evaluate their views which enhance their cognitive functioning and understanding of material learnt. Problem-solving involve activities and self-regulation in learning whereby student state problem, gather data and test them. The findings of this study is similar to that of Ali, Amdad, Akhter and Khan (2010); Kousar (2010); Ifamuyiwa and Ajilogba (2012); Nfon (2013); Gok (2014) who also discovered that students taught using problem-solving had higher achievement scores than conventional method students. The use of problem-solving and lecture method on academic performance of students brought out the similarity in the findings. The findings of this study is in contrast with the findings by Adu and Emunemu (2008) which showed no significant difference in economics achievement of students exposed to problem solving, concept mapping and lecture method, and Adeoye (2010) found that cooperative learning strategy students had higher achievement score than the problem-solving strategy students, also Jeotee (2012) reported that the problem-solving ability had negative influence on academic ability. The difference in the result of the findings may be due to the subject matters; that is, in this study respiratory system was taught using questioning and practical activities.

Conclusion

This study was carried out to determine the Impact of Problem-Solving Strategy on Performance in Respiratory System concept using STEM model among Secondary School Students in Zaria Educational Zone. From the findings the students taught using problem-solving strategy with STEM model recorded better performance than those taught with lecture teaching method. The characteristics of problem-solving strategy with STEM model are learner-centered and hence their team work, peer interactions, increases the students' performance. The methods of teaching teachers employed in the teaching and learning of Biology have impact on students' academic performance.

Recommendations

On the basis of these findings, the following recommendations are hereby suggested:

1. Biology teachers should be encouraged to explore problem-solving strategy with STEM model to improve academic performance of students.
2. In-service training for science teachers, seminar and workshops should be organized by the Ministry of Education for Biology teachers in secondary schools to employ problem-solving strategy with STEM model in the classrooms.
3. Federal and State Governments should provide both adequate instructional and infrastructural resources for the effective implementation of activity-based teaching strategy such as problem-solving strategy with STEM model.

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